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Wildflower seed sales as incentive for adopting flower strips for native bee conservation: a cost-benefit analysis.

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27 **Abstract**

28 Improving pollinator habitat on farmlands is needed to further wild bee conservation and to
29 sustain crop pollination in light of relationships between global declines in pollinators and
30 reductions in floral resources. One management strategy gaining much attention is the use of
31 wildflower strips planted alongside crops to provide supplemental floral resources for
32 pollinators. However, farmer adoption of pollinator-friendly strategies has been minimal, likely
33 due to uncertainty about costs and benefits of providing non-crop flowering plants for bees.
34 Over three years, on four diversified farms in Montana USA, we estimated the potential
35 economic profit of harvesting and selling wildflower seeds collected from flower strips
36 implemented for wild bee conservation, as an incentive for farmers to adopt this management
37 practice. We compared the potential profitability of selling small retail seed packets versus bulk
38 wholesale seed. Our economic analyses indicated that potential revenue from retail seed sales
39 exceeded the costs associated with establishing and maintaining wildflower strips after the
40 second growing season. A wholesale approach, in contrast, resulted in considerable net
41 economic losses. We provide proof-of-concept that, under retail scenarios, the sale of native
42 wildflower seeds may provide an alternative economic benefit that, to our knowledge, remains
43 unexplored. The retail seed-sales approach could encourage greater farmer adoption of
44 wildflower strips as a pollinator conservation strategy in agroecosystems. The approach could
45 also fill a need for regionally-produced, native wildflower seed for habitat restoration and
46 landscaping aimed at conserving native plants and pollinators.

47

48 **Keywords**

49 Economic benefits, Habitat management, Native plants, Pollinator conservation, Wild bees.

50 **Introduction**

51 Animal-mediated pollination is an ecosystem service of great economic, ecological, and
52 societal value (e.g., Losey and Vaughn 2006). Pollination services are particularly important in
53 agriculture; an estimated 15-30% of U.S. food production and 35% of global production depends
54 on animals for pollination (Allen-Wardell *et al.* 1998, Losey and Vaughn 2006, Klein *et al.*
55 2007).

56 Bees are important pollinators for crop and non-crop plant species (Michener 2007), and
57 managed honey bees (*Apis mellifera* L.) (Hymenoptera: Apidae) are the predominant crop
58 pollinators globally (Klein *et al.* 2007). However, declines in honey bee health (e.g., Ellis *et al.*
59 2010) and increased awareness of the risks of relying too heavily on one species for crop
60 pollination highlight the importance of wild bees (e.g., Winfree *et al.* 2007, Geldmann and
61 Gonzalez-Varo 2018). For example, wild bees are more efficient pollinators than honey bees for
62 many crops (e.g., blueberries, Javorek *et al.* 2002; raspberries and blackberries, Cane 2005;
63 tomatoes, Greenleaf and Kremen 2006; and squash, Hurd *et al.* 1971), and which contribute
64 significantly to crop pollination worldwide (Losey and Vaughn 2006, Klein *et al.* 2007, Gallai *et*
65 *al.* 2009, Garibaldi *et al.* 2013).

66 The development of farm-management strategies that encourage wild bee populations is an
67 important priority for sustainable agriculture (e.g., Goulson *et al.* 2015), especially given the
68 scarcity of non-crop flowering plants in highly-managed croplands (Biesmeijer *et al.* 2006, Potts
69 *et al.* 2010, Winfree *et al.* 2011). Farmers are often unable to modify the habitats surrounding
70 their fields. However, they can enact small-scale, bee-friendly habitat changes on their own
71 lands. One promising strategy is the use of native wildflower plantings (i.e., “flower strips”)
72 designed to supply continuous floral resources for bees beyond the blooming period of crops

73 (Tuell *et al.* 2008, Isaacs *et al.* 2009, Blaauw and Isaacs, 2014, Williams *et al.* 2015, Lundin *et*
74 *al.* 2018).

75 Farmers may be reluctant to adopt wildflower strips without better information on their
76 benefits and costs (Wratten *et al.* 2012, Blaauw and Isaacs 2014, Uyttenbroeck *et al.* 2016),
77 despite government incentives and cost-sharing programs directed at implementing farm-based
78 wildflower plantings (e.g., Vaughan and Skinner 2008, Haaland, Naisbit and Bersier 2011,
79 Batáry *et al.* 2015). Research documenting the value of flower plantings to support pollinators
80 primarily comes from Europe rather than North America (reviewed in Venturini *et al.* 2017a).
81 Globally, however, only a few studies have examined the economics of floral resource
82 provisioning for pollinators, including profits from increased crop yield and costs of
83 implementing these practices (e.g., Blaauw and Isaacs 2014, Pywell *et al.* 2015, Morandin *et al.*
84 2016, Venturini *et al.* 2017b). Additional research demonstrating economic benefits of
85 wildflower plantings will likely aid growers to decide whether to adopt this technique
86 (Vanslebrouck *et al.* 2002, Pascual and Perrings 2007, Uyttenbroeck *et al.* 2016). For
87 example, a recent economic experiment examining landowner enrollment decisions
88 demonstrated that without monetary incentives that outweigh the crop production value of that
89 land, adoption of pollinator habitat strategies are minimal (Jones Ritten *et al.* 2017). In addition,
90 those lands that are planted with pollinator habitat are lower quality lands (i.e., marginal lands
91 with low production value), which may provide low-quality pollinator habitat.

92 Not all pollinator-dependent crops experience increased pollination from pollinator habitat
93 management practices (Sardinas and Kremen 2015). Different bee communities respond to the
94 presence of wildflower plantings in different ways, ultimately affecting crop visitation rates and
95 pollination (Burkle *et al.* 2017). Furthermore, diversified farms, which are comparatively less-

96 studied in regards to flower plantings compared to intensive agroecosystems, may already
97 provide abundant and diverse floral resources, with maximal crop pollination even without
98 wildflower strips (Kennedy *et al.* 2013, Scheper *et al.* 2013, 2015). The lack of consistent crop-
99 yield benefits due to presence of wildflower strips might reduce farmer interest in pollinator
100 conservation. However, we are presently far from a practical understanding of the
101 environmental and economic benefits of wildflower strips within the numerous agroecosystems
102 across North America and globally.

103 Over the last 30 years, the demand for native plant products has grown along with increasing
104 awareness of the importance of native plants in a variety of applications, including revegetation
105 projects, wildlife habitat restoration, conservation plantings, landscaping, and public and private
106 gardens (Richards *et al.* 1998, Aldrich 2002, Potts *et al.* 2002, Norcini 2006, Erickson 2008,
107 Tuell *et al.* 2008, Isaacs *et al.* 2009, Peppin *et al.* 2010, Bujak 2015, Lundin *et al.* 2018). For
108 example, with respect to pollinators, the United States Department of Agriculture currently offers
109 a variety of incentive-based programs to establish habitat using native plants such as the
110 Pollinator Habitat Initiative (CP-42) under the Conservation Reserve Program (CRP) and the
111 Environmental Quality Incentive Program (EQIP) (Vaughan and Skinner 2008). More recently,
112 the U.S. government promoted a strategy focused on using native plants to “restore or enhance 7
113 million acres of land for pollinators over the next 5 years” (The White House 2015a). Current
114 revegetation policies already stress the use of native plants, but can easily be dismissed in certain
115 circumstances such as limited seed availability (Richards *et al.* 1998, Erickson 2008, USDA FS
116 2012). To avoid this problem, strategies are needed to increase local native-plant seed supplies
117 and establish seed reserves to ensure a stable and affordable native seed supply (White House

118 2015a, b). Partnering with farmers growing native plants as forage for pollinators might be one
119 relatively efficient way to increase seed availability.

120 To further explore the potential benefits of establishing on-farm pollinator habitats, we
121 planted native perennial-wildflower strips on four diversified farms in the Northern Rockies of
122 Montana USA. Over three years, we assessed whether wildflower strips could profit farmers via
123 native plant-seed sales beyond their associated costs. We examined retail and wholesale seed-
124 sales approaches. This was motivated by local (Bujak 2015) and national (e.g., Whitehouse
125 2015a, b) demand for native wildflower seeds. We are not aware of other studies evaluating
126 wildflower strips implemented for bee conservation as marketable wildflower seed sources.

127

128 **Materials and Methods**

129 *Study sites and flower strips*

130 This research was conducted in southwest Montana USA from 2013-2015 at four small,
131 diversified vegetable farms (i.e., market gardens) each having approximately 3-10 acres in
132 cultivation annually (Supp. Table S1). Each farm grew numerous, locally-marketed crops,
133 including squash and pumpkins (*Cucurbita pepo* L.), tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.), and
134 cucumbers (*Cucumis sativus* L.). Two farms were certified organic and the others followed
135 organic or sustainable practices. Honey bee colonies (≤ 5) were occasionally kept on-farm, but
136 all farms were located within a 5-mile radius of at least one commercial apiary
137 (<https://mtplants.mt.gov/Hypersensitive/BeeHyperSearch.aspx>). The farms, which were up to 30
138 km apart, varied in micro-climatic conditions, weed densities, and management practices,
139 including irrigation methods and planting bed preparation (Supp. Table S1).

140 We selected nine native perennial wildflower species for the flower strips: *Campanula*
141 *rotundifolia* L., *Erigeron speciosus* (Lindl.) DC., *Gaillardia aristata* Pursh, *Geranium*
142 *viscosissimum* Fisch. and C.A. Mey. Ex C.A. Mey., *Helianthus maximiliani* Schrad.,
143 *Heterotheca villosa* (Pursh) Shinnery, *Monarda fistulosa* L., *Penstemon confertus* Douglas ex
144 Lindl., and *Phacelia hastata* Douglas ex Lehm.. To provide pollen and nectar for a diversity of
145 bee species across each growing season, we chose species with different floral colors,
146 morphologies, and bloom phenologies (Tuell *et al.* 2008). Furthermore, we selected wildflower
147 species that thrive in full sun and are drought tolerant. These abiotic factors reflect typical
148 agricultural field conditions in this region.

149 In spring 2013, we started plants in the greenhouse in cone-tainers (SC10U-98 cells per tray)
150 from seed. In early June on each farm, we transplanted a total of 153 plugs into c. 1 x 33 m
151 strips prepared in a manner consistent with each farm's planting bed preparation methods (Supp.
152 Table S1). We used plugs rather than direct seeding to hasten flower-strip establishment and
153 enhance similarity among the farms. Each wildflower strip was planted with three, c. 1 m² -
154 replicates of each of the nine species for a total of 27 plots per strip and was positioned at one
155 edge of each farm, so as not to not interfere with farming activities.

156

157 ***Calculating costs and estimated profits associated with wildflower strips***

158 We recorded all labor (i.e., number of hours and people) and monetary costs associated with
159 1) establishing and maintaining flower strips (e.g., plant materials, planting the strips, weeding)
160 and 2) taking a seed-sales approach (e.g., hand-harvesting, cleaning, and packaging seed) from
161 2013-2015 for each farm. We considered two different suppliers for purchasing plant materials
162 for flower strips, including a local wholesale nursery and an online retail nursery specializing in

163 native plants. We also considered retail and wholesale selling approaches for estimating the
164 value of wildflower seeds. We calculated potential income from seed sales using our seed yields
165 for each year, farm, and wildflower species and 1) current retail values for seed packets
166 (USD/packet/unit weight) obtained by researching local and online seed vendors and 2) current
167 wholesale values for bulk seed obtained from a local wholesale seed company. To determine
168 overall potential net profit, we compared all costs incurred during 2013-2015 against the
169 projected income from retail and wholesale wildflower seed sales in 2014 and 2015 for 1) each
170 farm (i.e., the entire flower strip) and 2) each wildflower species individually, because each
171 species had unique attributes that contributed to the overall costs. Blaauw and Isaacs (2014)
172 used a labor rate of \$10/h in their analyses, but we increased that to \$12/h (USD) based on
173 guidance from a local nursery.

174

175 ***Costs of establishing and maintaining flower strips (2013-2015)***

176 *Plant material costs.* We estimated the cost to purchase plant materials using prices from
177 two commercial sources that specialize in native plants, a local Montana wholesale nursery that
178 charges \$1.30 per plug (Scenario 1; 2016 pricing) and an online retail nursery that charges \$3.66
179 per plug (Scenario 2; 2016 pricing).

180 *Planting costs.* Because we used perennials, planting costs were incurred only in 2013. For
181 each farm in 2013, we recorded the total time (h) to plant each wildflower strip, the number of
182 plugs planted of each species, and the total number of plugs of all species (Supp. Tables S2 and
183 S3). We calculated the proportion of plugs of each species planted (P_F), which was the same at
184 each farm (Supp. Table S2). We calculated the costs to plant each species per farm as: Planting
185 Cost = (total hours to plant strip x P_F) x (labor rate per hour) (Supp. Tables S2-S4).

186 *Watering costs.* At each farm, the wildflower strips were on the same grower-installed
187 irrigation system as adjacent crops. Therefore, the wildflower strips received irrigation when the
188 crops did regardless of whether they needed it. We did not factor this cost into our analysis
189 because this did not require any additional farmer labor or water costs. However, in 2013, the
190 flower strips required supplemental irrigation beyond the weekly crop watering to increase
191 establishment success, so we factored this cost into our analysis because it was additional labor
192 outside of normal farm operations. For each farm in 2013, we recorded the total time to hand-
193 water each wildflower strip (Supp. Table S3) and calculated watering costs for each species as:
194 $\text{Watering Cost} = (\text{total hours to water strip} \times P_F) \times (\text{labor rate per hour})$ (Supp. Tables S2-S4).

195 *Weeding costs.* For each farm in 2013-2015, we recorded the total time to weed each
196 wildflower strip (Supp. Table S3). In 2013 (year 1), all species required the same basic weeding
197 effort because of similar areas of bare soil around each plant regardless of species. Thus, we
198 calculated weeding cost for each species as: $\text{Weeding Cost} = (\text{total hours to weed strip} / \text{number}$
199 $\text{of flower species}) \times (\text{labor rate per hour})$ (Supp. Tables S2-S4). However, for 2014 and 2015,
200 weeding times varied among wildflower species based on the area of ground covered by our
201 plants, many of which had spread, covering much of the bare space between plants and
202 suppressing weed germination and growth. We realized this difference in effort between plant
203 species was important to consider in our analyses. Therefore, to distribute the overall weeding
204 effort for the entire strip among the different plant species, we created a simple index of relative
205 weeding effort for each wildflower species based on plant characteristics (i.e., spread, density,
206 size) that affected weeding effort. Species that were less time consuming to weed received a
207 score of 1, whereas those that were approximately twice as time consuming received a score of 2,
208 for a total of 12 units of effort across all nine species (Supp. Table S2). The proportion of

209 weeding effort for each species (P_w) thus equals the weeding index of each species divided by 12
210 (Supp. Table S2). We calculated weeding costs for each species in 2014 and 2015 as: Weeding
211 Cost = (total hours to weed strip x P_w) x (labor rate per hour) (Supp. Tables S2-S4). To ensure
212 that our indices were not leading to inaccuracies or biases, we also conducted a simple
213 robustness analysis in which we redid our overall cost-benefit calculations under the assumption
214 of equality of weeding effort among species.

215 *Opportunity costs.* For each farm in 2013-2015, we included the opportunity cost, or the cost
216 incurred from displacing other salable crops in order provide ground to plant wildflower strips,
217 for each of the four farms. We used the 43,560 Initiative (i.e., gross revenue goal of \$43,560 per
218 acre, or \$1 per ft²; net revenue goal of approximately half gross revenue, or \$0.50 per ft²) as a
219 guide to calculate gross and net revenue lost (Odeh and Hairston 2014). This model applies to
220 small, diversified farms with retail and direct-to-consumer sales. It likely overestimates the
221 actual value lost per foot through crop displacement on each farm (Pers. Comm., M. Burgess,
222 Assistant Professor, Montana State University, Bozeman, MT). For example, mean gross
223 revenue (2017) for 10 crops at one participating farm in our study was \$0.65 per ft² (Pers.
224 Comm., M. Burgess). Therefore, we calculated the net opportunity costs for the space each
225 flower species occupied each year as: Opportunity Cost = (area of flower strip in ft² x net
226 revenue per ft²) / (number of flower species) (Supp. Table S4). This cost was the same among
227 flower species and farms because each flower strip was the same size on each farm and each
228 flower species was provided the same amount of space to grow within the strip.

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232 ***Costs of harvesting, cleaning, testing, and packaging seed (2014-2015)***

233 *Seed harvesting cost.* For each farm in 2014, we recorded the total time to harvest seed from
234 each wildflower strip (Supp. Table S3). Species varied in the level of difficulty to collect seeds
235 due to plant traits, such as plant architecture, seed type and dispersal mechanism, and the
236 synchrony of seed maturation rates. For example, seeds of some species matured almost all at
237 once, while in other species seeds matured over several weeks and required multiple seed
238 collecting trips. Therefore, we created a simple index of relative harvesting effort for each
239 flower species based on these plant characteristics. Species for which it was relatively less time
240 consuming to harvest seed received a score of 1, whereas species for which it was most time
241 consuming to harvest seed received a score of 3, and those falling in between received a score of
242 2, for a total of 16 units of effort among all nine wildflower species (Suppl. Table S2). The
243 proportion of harvesting effort for each flower species (P_H) thus equals the harvesting index of
244 each species divided by 16 (Supp. Table S2). We calculated seed harvesting costs for each
245 species in 2014 as: Seed Harvesting Cost = (total hours to harvest seed in strip x P_H) x (labor rate
246 per hour) (Supp. Tables S2-S4). As with weeding effort (see *Weeding costs*), we also conducted
247 a simple robustness analysis in which we redid our overall cost-benefit calculations under the
248 assumption of equality of seed harvesting effort among species to ensure that our indices were
249 not leading to inaccuracies or biases. Because plants were generally similar in size during the
250 years we collected seed, we assumed that seed harvesting cost was the same in 2015 as in 2014
251 (Supp. Table S4).

252 *Seed cleaning costs.* We cleaned seeds by hand and used a series of wire-mesh sieves as
253 well as a seed blower (E.L. Erickson Products- Model B, Brookings, South Dakota) when it was
254 appropriate for the type of seed. For plant species with large awns, such as *E. speciosus*, *G.*

255 *aristata*, and *H. villosa*, we removed all non-seed plant debris by hand. In 2014, we recorded the
256 total time to clean seed of each wildflower species cumulatively across all farms, so we could not
257 calculate individual seed cleaning times for each farm (Supp. Table S5). However, in 2015, we
258 recorded the total time to clean seed of each species for each farm. This provided us with data
259 on the proportion of time spent cleaning seeds of each species on each farm in 2015, hereafter
260 referred to as $P_{C(\text{Farms } 1-4)}$ (Supp. Table S2). Therefore, for 2014 analyses, we assumed a similar
261 proportion of time cleaning seeds as in 2015 and calculated an estimated seed cleaning cost for
262 each species at each farm as: Seed Cleaning Cost = (total hours to clean seed of each species x
263 $P_{C(\text{Farm})}$) x (labor rate per hour) (Supp. Tables S2 and S4). For 2015, seed cleaning costs for each
264 species at each farm were calculated as: Seed Cleaning Cost = total hours to clean seed of each
265 species x labor rate per hour (Supp. Table S4).

266 *Seed lab testing costs.* Though not required by Federal Seed Act Regulations for
267 wildflowers, we included the cost of testing seed for germination and viability (\$56 per species
268 per year) and purity (\$39 per species per year) by the Montana State Seed Laboratory as it is
269 good practice for ensuring quality seed for sale (Supp. Table S4). Germination testing measures
270 seedling emergence and development. Seeds that do not germinate may be dormant and are then
271 tested for viability using a Tetrazolium (TZ) test (AOSA 2017). Purity measures the percent of a
272 wildflower seed lot that is the species of interest versus weed seeds, other seeds, or inert debris.
273 Due to the expense involved with seed testing, we only requested TZ tests for our seed lots to
274 determine seed viability. We used results of the TZ tests as an overall indicator of total seed lot
275 viability. For our analyses, we considered our harvested seed samples to be 100% wildflower
276 seeds (i.e., only wildflower seed) because we harvested seed in small batches by hand, resulting

277 in very clean seed samples lacking debris and non-wildflower seed, though such purity was not
278 measured explicitly.

279 *Seed packing costs: retail only.* In order to estimate the number of packets that could be
280 filled for each of the wildflower species, we determined the amount of seed contained in retail
281 packets and then converted this to seed weight per packet using information on seed count per
282 unit weight contained in the Association of Official Seed Analysts (AOSA) rule book (i.e., set of
283 standard procedures in the United States and Canada for testing seeds) (Supp. Table S6).

284 *Penstemon confertus* and *P. hastata* are not sold commercially, so we estimated seed numbers
285 per packet for these species based on similar plant species (i.e., other species in the same genus
286 with seeds of similar size, including *Penstemon hirsutus* (L.) Willd. and *Phacelia campanularia*
287 A. Gray). When information on weight was not available for the species of interest in the AOSA
288 rule book, we used the closest species available within the genus with similarly sized seeds. If
289 there were no similar species for comparison, we used reported numbers of seeds per unit weight
290 from various online seed companies that also sell seed in larger quantities (Prairie Moon
291 Nursery, Native Ideals Seed Farm, Planet Natural, High Country Gardens, and Great Basin
292 Seed). It should be noted, however, that seed weight may vary considerably within and between
293 species depending on production practices, environmental effects, and harvest timing. We then
294 used the results of our TZ tests (% seed viability) to adjust the weight of seed per packet until we
295 reached a minimum of 90% seed viability for each flower species (Supp. Table S7) to ensure
296 quality seed for sale as: Adjusted Seed Packet Weight = (weight of seed per retail packet x 90%
297 seed viability) / (actual % seed viability per flower species) (Supp. Table S7). We estimated the
298 total number of seed packets we could fill by hand based on the total weight of seed collected
299 from each wildflower species as: Total Number Seed Packets = total weight of seed per flower

300 species / adjusted weight per seed packet (Supp. Tables S7 and S8). We estimated the total cost
301 required to package all seeds of each species for each farm as: Seed Packaging Cost = (total
302 number of seed packets filled per wildflower species / number of seed packets filled per hour) x
303 (labor rate per hour) (Supp. Table S4, S6 and S8).

304 *Seed envelope costs: retail only.* For our analyses we chose plain coin envelopes (5.72 x
305 8.89 cm), which cost \$0.06 each and are what a small producer might use when selling at
306 farmer's markets. More elaborate packaging strategies involving custom-printed packaging
307 would thus have to take this into account. We did not consider the cost of labeling the envelopes
308 since there are numerous options that will depend on the producer. For 2014 and 2015, we
309 multiplied the total number of seed packets needed per flower species (Supp. Table S8) by \$0.06
310 per envelope to estimate, for each farm, the cost of envelopes to package seed of each flower
311 species (Supp. Table S4).

312 *Seed licensing costs.* Though not required in the state of Montana for selling wildflower
313 seed, we included the cost of a seed license because other states may require this. The cost is
314 \$225 per farm per year and includes a Dealer license (\$75), Labeler license (\$75), and Seed
315 Grower license (\$75) (Supp. Table S4). We distributed this cost evenly among the nine
316 wildflower species (\$25 per species) for analyses.

317

318 ***Income from seed sales (2014-2015)***

319 *Retail seed-sales.* For each flower species, we determined the local and regional retail
320 pricing for seed packets (\$1.95-3.99 per packet; Supp. Table S6). For *P. confertus* and *P.*
321 *hastata*, which are not sold commercially, we estimated the value based on similar species (i.e.,
322 other species in the same genus with similarly sized seeds or species with a similar level of seed

323 harvesting difficulty; *P. hirsutus* and *Penstemon eriantherus* Pursh var. *argillosus* M.E. Jones;
324 Pers. Comm. J. Scianna, USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service, Bridger Plant
325 Materials Center, Bridger, MT). When multiple prices were found for a species, we used the
326 lowest price as a conservative estimate. For 2014 and 2015, we multiplied the total number of
327 seed packets per wildflower species (Supp. Table S8) by the current market value per packet to
328 determine the potential income from seed sales of each flower species and the entire flower strip
329 for each farm (Supp. Table S9).

330 *Wholesale seed-sales.* For each flower species, we determined the wholesale value for bulk
331 seeds using a local seed company (Bruce Seed Farm Inc., Townsend, MT). Values ranged from
332 \$28-150 per PLS pound (PLS, or pure live seed, is the percentage of seed that will germinate
333 within a given quantity and is calculated as: % PLS = (% seed purity x % seed viability) / 100
334 (Supp. Table S6). No bulk pricing was available for three of the species (i.e., *C. rotundifolia*, *P.*
335 *confertus* and *P. hastata*). Therefore, we based pricing on the level of seed harvesting difficulty,
336 size of seeds, and lack of commercial availability. We used the higher value of \$150 per PLS
337 pound as an estimate of value; the lack of seed availability may warrant even higher market
338 values (Pers. Comm. G. Pearse, Bruce Seed Farm Inc., Townsend, MT). For 2014 and 2015, we
339 determined the value of bulk seed for each species per farm using the following equation: Bulk
340 Seed Value = ((total weight of seed collected for each species per farm x % PLS) / 100) x
341 (market value of bulk seed) (Supp. Tables S6-S8).

342

343 ***Cost-benefit analysis (2013-2015)***

344 *Retail seed-sales.* For each year and farm, we summed all costs associated with 1)
345 establishing and maintaining the flower strips using Scenario 2 (i.e., higher plug cost) for

346 purchasing plant materials as a conservative estimate of profit and 2) taking a retail seed-sales
347 approach for each wildflower species (Supp. Tables S4 and S9). For each year and farm, we also
348 summed all potential income from retail seed sales for each species (Supp. Table S9). We
349 calculated the overall potential net profit as: $\text{Net Profit} = \text{income from seed sales} - \text{cost to}$
350 $\text{establish and maintain strips} - \text{cost to process seeds for sale}.$

351 *Wholesale seed-sales.* We used the same equation above for the wholesale seed sales cost-
352 benefit analysis, except that we used Scenario 1 (i.e., lower plug cost) for purchasing plant
353 materials as a conservative estimate of losses (Supp. Tables S4 and S9).

354

355 **Results**

356 *Costs of establishing and maintaining wildflower strips (2013-2015).*

357 Overall costs associated with establishing and maintaining wildflower strips varied among
358 farms, flower species, and years (Figs. 1 and 2, Supp. Tables S3 and S4). The largest expense
359 associated with establishing and maintaining wildflower strips for all farms was the cost to
360 purchase plant materials for the entire flower strip and depended on whether plugs were to be
361 purchased from a wholesale (Scenario 1) or retail (Scenario 2) nursery (Supp. Table S4). Cost
362 estimates also varied among flower species. We also saw differences among farms in costs to
363 plant wildflower strips, due to differences among farms in planting bed preparation (Tables S1,
364 S3, and S4). Because we planted each flower species at different densities to maximize the use
365 of space and floral display for pollinators, there were also differences in estimated mean costs
366 among species resulting from the increased labor to plant and water the species requiring more
367 plugs to be planted due to smaller growth habits (i.e., plant height and spread) (Supp. Table S10).
368 Weeding costs varied among farms for the entire flower strip in all three years (Supp. Tables S3

369 and S4). Estimated mean costs associated with weeding in 2013 were the same among flower
370 species because of similarities in the amount of bare ground compared to the initial size of the
371 plugs. In subsequent years, as plants grew larger, estimated mean costs associated with weeding
372 varied among flower species (Supp. Table S10). Another large expense was the yearly
373 opportunity cost associated with displacing other salable crops to provide space for the
374 wildflower strips, which was the same among flower species and farms (Supp. Table S4).

375

376 *Costs of harvesting, cleaning, testing, and packaging seed (2014-2015).*

377 Overall costs associated with collecting seeds and preparing them for sale varied among
378 farms, wildflower species, and years (Figs. 1 and 2, Supp. Tables S3, S4, and S10). The largest
379 expense associated with taking a seed-sales approach was seed testing and licensing, which was
380 the same for each farm and flower species (Supp. Tables S4 and S10). Estimated mean costs of
381 seed harvesting were among the lowest expense incurred and varied by flower species in 2014
382 and in 2015 (Supp. Tables S3 and S10). Seed harvesting costs also varied among farms for the
383 entire flower strip (Supp. Tables S3 and S4). Estimated mean costs of cleaning seed varied
384 among flower species in 2014 and 2015 (Supp. Table S10). Seed cleaning costs also varied
385 among farms for the entire flower strip (Supp. Tables S3 and S4). Estimated costs of packaging
386 seed and of seed envelopes, incurred by retail seed sales only, varied among flower species and
387 farm in 2014 and 2015 (Supp. Tables S3, S4, and S10). Differences among flower species in
388 seed viability affected the total amount of salable seed and also affected seed packaging and seed
389 envelope costs for the retail seed-sales approach (Supp. Tables S4 and S7).

390

391

392 ***Income from seed sales (2014-2015).***

393 We observed large differences among farms and years in the potential income from retail and
394 wholesale seed sales for the entire flower strip (Supp. Table S9). We also saw large differences
395 among wildflower species in potential income from 1) retail seed sales, with *H. villosa* having
396 the highest potential mean income in 2014 and 2015, *G. viscosissimum* having the lowest income
397 in 2014, and *P. hastata* the lowest in 2015 (Fig. 1, Supp. Table S11) and 2) wholesale seed sales,
398 with *E. speciosus* having the highest potential mean income in 2014 and 2015, *G. viscosissimum*
399 having the lowest income in 2014, and *C. rotundifolia* the lowest in 2015 (Fig. 2, Supp. Table
400 S11).

401

402 ***Cost-benefit analysis (2013-2015)***

403 *Retail seed-sales: net estimated profit.* In the overall retail cost-benefit analysis conducted
404 across all four farms and all three years, we projected that all farms would profit from seed sales,
405 when considering the entire flower strip (Fig. 3, Table 1). However, estimated total profits
406 varied greatly among farms due, for example, to differences in planting and weeding costs
407 resulting from planting bed preparation (i.e., management practices) (Supp. Tables S1, S3, and
408 S4). Across farms, we projected that seven of the nine wildflower species would be profitable
409 from retail seed sales, but estimated profits varied greatly among the flower species (Fig. 3,
410 Table 1). We conducted subsequent robustness analyses to validate the weeding and seed
411 harvesting effort indices we used for calculating weeding and seed harvesting costs for the
412 overall cost-benefit analyses. These analyses showed some differences among plant species, but
413 supported the same overall patterns of profitability across all nine species. Therefore, we

414 retained the weeding and seed harvesting indices for all analyses because they more accurately
415 reflected the difference among plant species.

416 *Wholesale seed-sales: net estimated loss.* In the overall wholesale cost-benefit analysis
417 conducted across all four farms and all three years, we projected that all farms would suffer
418 similar losses from seed sales, when considering the entire flower strip (Fig. 3, Table 1).
419 Estimated losses were also similar among the flower species (Fig. 3, Table 1).

420

421 **Discussion**

422 One of the primary motivations for adopting wildflower strips on farmlands is to increase
423 crop yields. Such benefits should accrue via enhanced pollination services provided when wild
424 bees are more abundant and diverse in the presence of supplemental floral resources. However,
425 other potential benefits remain poorly understood. To our knowledge, among the ecological and
426 economic benefits of pollinator habitat plantings considered to date (reviewed in Uyttenbroeck *et*
427 *al.* 2016, Venturini *et al.* 2017a), the role of flower strips in native wildflower seed production
428 has not been explored (but see Todd *et al.* 2016 on using sunflower crops as pollinator
429 resources). Our economic analyses indicate that revenue from the retail sale, but not bulk
430 wholesale, of wildflower seed collected from flower strips on four small, diversified farms could
431 exceed the costs associated with establishing and maintaining flower strips after the second
432 growing season. Such an approach may provide an economic incentive to encourage greater
433 adoption of this pollinator conservation strategy.

434 The same small farms where we conducted the research reported here harbor >202 wild bee
435 species (Delphia *et al.* 2019), most of which visited the wildflower strips for food resources
436 (Burkle, Delphia, O'Neill, unpublished data). Thus our flower strips helped support high bee

437 diversity. In addition to the ecological benefits, our economic analysis indicates that selling
438 seeds from wildflower strips via retail sale, but not wholesale, has potential to provide an
439 economic advantage. The differences in profitability we observed depended on factors
440 associated with the farm (i.e., weed pressure, planting bed preparation) that affected planting and
441 weeding costs as well as wildflower growth, flowering, and ultimately seed production. Other
442 factors affecting profitability included differences between wildflower species in costs associated
443 with weeding and with processing and cleaning seeds. Our findings indicate that some
444 wildflower species may be more profitable to grow for seed sales than others and the discrepancy
445 in profitability can further be affected by local climate and farm management practices. Income
446 could potentially be even higher if farmers took a targeted approach of collecting seeds only
447 from those species with the greatest profitability each year, yet still providing a diverse suite of
448 plants for pollinators by growing all species.

449 Retail seed sales require added labor for filling individual seed packets, which may provide a
450 disincentive to some farmers. Thus, we explored bulk seed sales as a potentially more attractive
451 and less time-intensive option. However, our wildflower strips were not large enough to make a
452 wholesale seed-sales approach viable after accounting for 1) the low amount of seed harvested
453 per species at each farm (i.e., flower strips only produced a pound of seed at two farms for three
454 plant species in 2014 and at one farm for one species in 2015), 2) the low percentage pure live
455 seed (PLS) often typical of wildflower seed, which substantially lowers the amount of salable
456 seed (e.g., PLS for seed from our flower species ranged from 16.5% to 99%, depending on the
457 farm, species, and year), and 3) the much lower price per unit weight compared to retail seed
458 sales. For example, a farmer would need to produce anywhere from c. 1.5 to 11 lbs of seed per
459 species with 100% PLS just to break even in the second year. Alternatively, a farmer could take

460 a targeted approach and focus on growing those species with the highest bulk value, but this
461 could reduce the overall floral (and perhaps bee) diversity within the strips if limited space is a
462 concern. Larger-scale plantings would also likely require alternative weeding methods and
463 mechanized seed harvesting to lower labor costs associated with hand-weeding flower strips and
464 hand-harvesting seed. Opportunity costs of displacing salable crops would also be increased
465 with larger flower plantings unless flower plantings were placed on field margins or other non-
466 crop lands. Several of the species that we grew in our flower strips are not currently available
467 for wholesale, despite known conservation value to bees (e.g., *P. hastata*; Ogle *et al.* 2011,
468 2012), likely because the methods to mechanically harvest seed on a large scale have not yet
469 been fully resolved (LeFebvre *et al.* 2017). For other species, it may be that the market (or
470 demand) does not yet exist to make wholesale seed production a viable option. Therefore,
471 assigning value to these species may overestimate the reported profitability and is a limitation of
472 our study.

473 Our research suggests that farmers planting flower strips could help fill the increasing need
474 for locally produced, regionally appropriate, native wildflower seed for use in a multitude of
475 applications, including other pollinator and wildlife habitat conservation projects and post-fire
476 restoration (e.g., Tuell *et al.* 2008, Isaacs *et al.* 2009, Peppin *et al.* 2010, USDA-FS 2012, The
477 White House 2015a, b). One seed mix or suite of native plants will not be sufficient to use
478 across all regions since flower species may vary in their attractiveness or ability to support the
479 local bee fauna (e.g., Williams *et al.* 2015). Therefore, this native seed production strategy could
480 be replicated regionally to produce seed from different suites of plant species suitable to each
481 habitat and tailored to the local pollinators.

482 To implement this strategy, seeds could be marketed with an indication that they originated
483 from farms actively engaged in pollinator conservation. Such marketing strategies have been
484 successfully employed for food products grown on farms that have adopted a conservation-
485 minded farming protocol (e.g., ‘Fair to Nature’ in the U.K. (<http://www.conservaiongrade.org>)
486 and Bee Better CertifiedTM in the U.S. (<http://beebettercertified.org>). Some farmers might also
487 be interested in not only the increased income, but enhanced social capital for their role in
488 supporting this practice. Farmers desiring to establish pollinator habitat, but without interest or
489 time to be directly involved in harvesting and selling wildflower seed, could develop
490 partnerships with seed producers, retailers, or plant nurseries that harvest the seed in exchange
491 for yearly maintenance associated with wildflower plantings.

492 Only a few studies have documented the costs required to plant and maintain wildflower
493 strips (e.g., Blaauw and Isaacs 2014, Venturini *et al.* 2017b). In our study, most of the costs
494 associated with flower strips were incurred in the first year with a subsequent yearly baseline
495 investment in weeding. Providing information on the costs of this pollinator-conservation
496 strategy allows farmers to make informed decisions on whether they can afford to implement this
497 approach when economic return is either delayed or unrealized. For example, crop yields
498 attributed to increased pollination may be crop- or region-specific (Sardinias and Kremen 2015)
499 and require a number of years to offset the costs of flower plantings (e.g., Blaauw and Isaacs
500 2014, Venturini *et al.* 2017b), thereby making it difficult to predict potential profits. The
501 approach that we have outlined for increasing revenue may allow for more predictability (though
502 bulk wildflower seed pricing can be highly volatile between years) and a quicker return rate on
503 the initial investment. For some farmers, however, supporting wild bees and increased farmland
504 biodiversity may be reason enough to provide pollinator habitat.

505 Another yearly expense of implementing wildflower strips was the opportunity cost
506 associated with loss of ground that could be used for other salable crops. This cost will vary
507 with the farming system/type, the crops being displaced, market values, and the geographic
508 region. For our purposes, we used a net revenue value targeted at small-scale, diversified farms
509 with retail and direct-to-consumer sales. Therefore, we potentially overestimated net revenue
510 when calculating opportunity costs. However, we consider our analysis to be a useful illustration
511 of some of the costs and benefits of planting wildflower strips rather than an economic analysis
512 that applies to all situations. One strategy to reduce opportunity cost would be to place
513 wildflower strips on areas of farms that are less ideal or unsuitable for crop production. Indeed,
514 the type of land selected by landowners for enrollment into pollinator habitat conservation is that
515 with low crop production value (Jones Ritten *et al.* 2017).

516 Understanding the full range of costs and benefits of pollinator habitat plantings enables
517 farmers to make informed decisions regarding adoption of such strategies (Uyttenbroeck *et al.*
518 2016, Venturini *et al.* 2017a). In addition to providing forage for wild bees, enhancing
519 pollination services in some cropping systems, and now providing native seed for potential sales,
520 non-crop flower plantings can serve many other important roles, such as enhancing soil nitrogen
521 when flowering leguminous cover crops are used in crop rotations (Ellis and Barbercheck 2015),
522 supporting natural enemies for pest suppression (Blaauw and Isaacs 2015), reducing soil erosion
523 (Wratten *et al.* 2012, Ellis and Barbercheck 2015), and providing windbreaks that reduce wind
524 speed and benefit crop yields (Vaughan and Black 2006). More research is needed to understand
525 some of the other environmental and economic benefits of wildflower strips within the numerous
526 agroecosystems across North America and the globe.

527 Our cost-benefit analyses for both retail and wholesale seed sales included three years of
528 empirical data based on our farm partners and small-scale flower strip plantings (< 1% of the
529 cropped area) and our local resources (nurseries and seed companies). We note that profits from
530 retail seed sales would have been higher if we used the lower plug costs to calculate net profits.
531 Similarly losses from wholesale seed sales would have been greater if we used the higher plug
532 costs to calculate net losses. It should also be noted that our estimated profits from retail sales
533 assumes a best-case scenario where a market is available for all seeds produced. Often farmers
534 growing vegetable seed for sale to larger commercial companies are contracted to grow
535 particular species projected to be in demand. Thus, each farmer would have to assess the
536 available market and determine costs associated with the inability to sell all seeds harvested or
537 develop partnerships with potential seed buyers beforehand. However, a farmer would not need
538 to sell all seed to at least break even. In addition, wildflowers would presumably continue to
539 produce seed beyond the study period as they are perennials, therefore potentially providing a
540 continued source of revenue. Further research will be needed to fully evaluate and optimize this
541 seed-sales approach for pollinator conservation in other farming systems and regions of the
542 country, but our findings provide a first step and suggest much potential.

543

544 **Author's Contributions**

545 CMD, LAB, and KMO conceived the ideas, designed methodology, and conducted to the cost-
546 benefit analysis. CMD coordinated field work with assistance of LAB and KMO. CMD wrote
547 the first draft of the manuscript and all authors contributed critically to subsequent drafts and
548 gave final approval for publication.

549

550 **Acknowledgements**

551 This project was supported by a Western Sustainable Agriculture Research and Education grant
552 (SW13-043) awarded to LAB, CMD, and KMO. We thank Laura Smith and Robert Dunn
553 (Westscape Wholesale Nursery) for providing helpful comments on the manuscript. We thank
554 participating farmers Matt and Jacy Rothschiller, Pete and Nancy Fay, John and Conni Mahoney,
555 Charles Holt, and Macdonald Burgess; field and laboratory assistants Jess Monte, Cecilia Welch,
556 Alisha Gill, and Melissa Bakosh; Justin Runyon for technical support; the MT State Seed Lab for
557 use of equipment and helpful advice; and Joseph Scianna (Bridger Plant Materials Center) and
558 Gordon Pearse (Bruce Seed Farm Inc.) for advice on wholesale and retail seed pricing. The
559 authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

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800 **Figure 1.** Mean (\pm SE) yearly (A) cost to establish and maintain flower strips (Cost 1), (B) cost
 801 to undertake a retail seed-sales approach (Cost 2), (C) total cost (Cost 1 + 2), (D) estimated
 802 potential income from retail seed sales, and (E) estimated net profit for each wildflower species
 803 among four farms. All values in USD.

805 **Figure 2.** Mean (\pm SE) yearly (A) cost to establish and maintain flower strips (Cost 1), (B) cost
 806 to undertake a wholesale seed-sales approach (Cost 2), (C) total cost (Cost 1 + 2), (D) estimated
 807 potential income from bulk wholesale seed sales, and (E) estimated net loss for each wildflower
 808 species among four farms. All values in USD.

810 **Figure 3.** Mean (\pm SE) estimated net profits (USD) from retail and wholesale seed sales cost-
811 benefit analysis (2013-2015) for each wildflower species among four farms.

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824 **Table 1.** Total estimated net profits (USD) from retail seed sales and net losses from wholesale
 825 seed sales cost-benefit analysis (2013-2015) for each wildflower species on each of four farms.

Scientific name	Farm			
	1	2	3	4
	Retail Seed-Sales			
<i>H. villosa</i>	8270.66	4445.34	1724.14	26589.03
<i>P. confertus</i>	3568.78	3223.43	3164.88	7533.49
<i>G. aristata</i>	7193.19	671.05	1156.69	5263.52
<i>M. fistulosa</i>	4721.15	2638.90	22.62	3816.22
<i>H. maximiliani</i>	1258.17	721.41	99.59	3498.32
<i>C. rotundifolia</i>	-77.97	153.56	-447.40	3146.47
<i>E. speciosus</i>	389.85	9.05	-160.59	112.18
<i>P. hastata</i>	-331.30	-419.82	-375.22	71.92
<i>G. viscosissimum</i>	-413.45	-364.94	-411.82	-330.64
Total (2 years income)	24579.07	11077.98	4772.89	49700.51
	Wholesale Seed-Sales			
<i>H. villosa</i>	-410.48	-420.20	-476.65	-417.83
<i>P. confertus</i>	-376.63	-386.30	-405.95	-337.56
<i>G. aristata</i>	-378.30	-410.93	-413.27	-402.43
<i>M. fistulosa</i>	-538.81	-526.91	-426.05	-465.53
<i>H. maximiliani</i>	-745.88	-505.40	-560.64	-617.52
<i>C. rotundifolia</i>	-395.08	-432.36	-465.82	-412.36
<i>E. speciosus</i>	-371.60	-401.15	-432.69	-391.79
<i>P. hastata</i>	-380.12	-414.79	-459.46	-415.24
<i>G. viscosissimum</i>	-527.15	-459.44	-440.03	-538.68
Total (2 years income)	-4124.05	-3957.48	-4080.55	-3998.95